

MAIN MODERN ASPECTS OF MARKETING IN FITNESS INDUSTRY IN THE CASE OF HIGH LEVEL OF MARKET COMPETITIVENESS

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Abstract

The popularity of fitness among the population has led to an increase in the number of enterprises providing these services. With increasing competition and a decrease in the solvency of the population due to the economic crisis in the Kazakh economy, the issue of promoting fitness services arises. The market for fitness services, from the point of view of scientific understanding, has been practically unstudied. However, modern domestic science has accumulated some experience in studying the marketing of services. This article discusses the issues of promoting fitness services in the modern Kazakhstan market.

Keywords: Fitness, fitness business, marketing, promotion, marketing in fitness industry, marketing instruments.

Currently, the services of fitness centers are among the ten most popular services in Kazakhstan. The growing level of well-being of residents of both large and small cities leads to the fact that the population begins to pay increased attention to their health, physical condition and appearance. Moreover, the need is growing precisely for high-quality services, which can only be provided by modern, well-equipped sports and health clubs and fitness centers. People want not only to play sports, but also to have a good time in their free time. After all, playing sports is one of the components of our leisure time. With a high level of competition in the fitness services market, where each fitness club is trying to increase the number of its clients by meeting their specific needs, the question of studying the marketing mix is certainly relevant.

A fitness service is a process that occurs between the client and the club providing the service. This is a deeply individual process, since the service is consumed at the time it is provided. If you are not satisfied with the product, you can exchange it or get your money back. This cannot be done with the service. You will not be able to refuse, for example, a poorly conducted training session, the instructor being late, or the reception staff making mistakes [1]. Moreover, more often than not, it is generally impossible to objectively demonstrate to the client whether the service is good or not until the moment, it is provided. Based on the above, certain conclusions can be drawn.

Firstly, a fitness service, like any other service, is intangible and intangible until the moment of its acquisition. In addition, in order for the client to take his word for it, service providers try to formalize the most significant service parameters for the buyer and present them as clearly as possible. In the fitness industry, this can be done with the help of a stylish and impressive design of a fitness club, high-quality service, modern equipment and new exercise equipment, highly qualified instructors, and so on. Because the intangibility of a service increases the risk of uncertainty when purchasing it, consumers listen more to other people's evaluations of the service than to advertising messages paid for by the service provider [2].

Therefore, the service provider (in our case, a fitness club) must stimulate the maintenance of a positive

public opinion by directing its marketing efforts to influencers (trying to awaken in them a desire to use the services of a sports and fitness center) and satisfied customers (so that they recommend the fitness club to their colleagues, friends and relatives).

Secondly, services are inseparable from the sources (specific workers) providing them. Any replacement of a trainer, instructor in a gym or aerobic gym can change the process and result of providing fitness services, and, consequently, change demand. Thus, both clients and sellers of fitness services influence the result of service [3].

Third, services are inconsistent in quality. This is due, first, to their inseparability from the performing subjects (the result of a fitness service even depends on the mood of the master), as well as to the impossibility and impracticality of defining strict standards for the processes and results of service provision. Nevertheless, service organizations, including fitness clubs, are trying to take various quality control measures. First, this is a careful selection and training of personnel [2]. In addition, it is possible to increase the motivation of employees by using incentives directly related to the quality of services. For this purpose, bonuses are introduced, such as "employee of the month", or various bonuses depending on customer reviews.

Fourth, services are not preserved. This means that it is impossible to prepare services in full in advance and store them as tangible goods in anticipation of an increase in demand. For example, if no one comes to a yoga class held in a fitness center, then the service simply disappears. As a rule, sports and health clubs encounter this kind of difficulties during the daytime, when the number of visitors is small. Moreover, during peak hours, that is, in the morning and evening, the situation is opposite: many clients cannot get to classes because the groups are overcrowded. To cope with these difficulties, many fitness centers use a price differentiation strategy that allows them to regulate demand, or rather reduce it during peak periods [4].

Marketing of fitness services is based on the general concept of marketing, since the modern service market offers the physical culture and sports industry a mechanism through which their commercialization is

carried out. Marketing includes analysis, planning, implementation and control of activities aimed at establishing profitable exchanges with target markets to achieve the goals of the fitness club.

The introduction of innovations into the daily activities of fitness clubs occurs according to a certain algorithm, which includes a number of preparatory and executive stages associated with the development and implementation of this business project. For this purpose, a business plan is drawn up, which is a comprehensive program that contains economic, technical, organizational measures, as well as provides forecast estimates and the necessary justification for the implementation of this project in practice [5].

Marketing management in the fitness industry is all about demand management. Demand is a social need for various services, a form of manifestation of need in the services market. The growing demand for fitness services entails an increase in supply. In this case, the winners are those market participants whose offers correspond to the basic preferences of the consumer. Speaking about consumer preferences, it is worth noting that some of the main criteria when choosing a fitness club are its location, pricing policy and range of services provided.

Let us look at the main reputation management tools used by fitness clubs in their daily activities.

Creating an attractive image for a fitness club through the fame and popularity of its employees and clients. High authority, fame and glory of the fitness club staff and its clientele play a huge role in the formation of reputation and good name.

Using expert reviews and media publications. Many fitness club websites contain corresponding sections called "Press about us" or "Publications", where excerpts or full texts of articles and reviews on the fitness industry are given, and where the brands of these clubs are mentioned in a favorable context.

Use of specialized ratings. A high place in the ranking compiled by a group of independent experts raises the business reputation of a fitness club among clients, partners and its own staff, and creates a basis for quantitative assessment of the most important parameters of the fitness business [6].

Conducting all kinds of competitions. The practice of running a modern fitness business shows that providing only high-quality services to club clients is not enough. It is necessary to arouse interest among consumers, create proper motivation for classes, for communication with staff and with each other. Such interest and communication are greatly facilitated by competitions held in a variety of areas and forms.

Comparison of training results according to the "before" and "after" criteria. Significant parts of clients come to fitness clubs with the goal of improving their figure and getting rid of excess weight. The motive of improving health and increasing physical activity is also important. By systematically measuring anthropological indicators and health status, clients have visible results of their exercises - photographs "before" and "after" of a certain stage of exercise, weight loss, muscle building, correction of body shape, posture, flexibility, endurance, strength.

The leading factor in the competitiveness of fitness industry enterprises is price. The cost of services provided to consumers determines the number of client groups, cash flow, profit and profitability of the fitness club. Price is a complex, integral indicator that includes a lot of other parameters of the economic activity of a fitness club. In particular, the price for fitness services includes:

- Production costs (including employee wages and investment costs);
- The profit margin of the fitness club or each individual service;
- Prestige and business reputation of the club;
- Personnel qualifications;
- Payment method for fitness services;
- Successful or unsuccessful location of the fitness club and some other parameters [3].

There are a number of other reputation management tools. These, in particular, include holding open days, press conferences, and corporate evenings for clients, fitness conventions, allocating places for fitness classes for children, the disabled, and much more.

All these events brought to the attention of the public through the media or otherwise, contribute to the formation of a good name for the fitness club. It is impeccable business reputation, which has high moral and economic significance. Increasing awareness of the club's brand and increasing the number of client groups is the main result that fitness business organizers expect to receive from the advertising campaign. Fitness clubs widely use various types of advertising in their commercial activities, influencing different target groups in a variety of ways.

Most often, advertising for fitness clubs appeals to aesthetic feelings, leadership, energy, economy, prestige, the joy of communication, and changes in life. Advertising stories and messages use, for the most part, approaches based on sexuality, attractiveness, life success, longevity, spiritual and physical health [7].

The fitness center needs to sell other services besides cards. This could be personal training, solarium, cosmetologist services. The presence of additional services will increase the throughput of the fitness center per unit of time and increase the turnover.

To summarize, we note that the main marketing technologies used in the fitness industry are analysis and forecasting of the state and development of the target market for health services. Identifying the needs of target groups for sports and recreational services; creating and ensuring flexible maneuvering in the field of pricing policy for services and goods; organization of work of fitness clubs; advertising, public relations. When applied, marketing technologies allow a company to achieve profitability and efficiency in the market through planning, organizing work, analyzing and monitoring the results of the company's market activities, its competitors and the market situation.

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